

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

this is a very special issue: the last of 12 in the 12th volume of J.UCS! J.UCS has grown over the years tremendously, in importance and size, and it will continue this way. The fact that J.UCS is now available for free for everyone due to the generosity of a number of academic institutions will further increase impact and importance of the journal. Do spread the news: here is a reviewed publication, with a comparatively short turn-around cycle that appears first electronically, but then also always in printed editions. By the way, most of the printed volumes are still available and can be ordered via http://www.jucs.org/jucs_info/print if you or your library are interested.

Turning to the content of this issue, it is typical for J.UCS: its internationality and the fact that J.UCS is not shying away from hot issues: if you read the paper on Web Search Engine Monopoly, the second paper in this issue, you will see what I mean.

Today, I also have an important message to all J.UCS authors whose papers have been published in our journal over the past 12 years: don't forget to look up your article now and then (SEARCH for your name does a superb job!) and enter remarks about similar papers you have written since, and PLEASE supply your home page, all this as part of the COMMENT field, so that others can easily learn more about you. We are preparing a big surprise for all J.UCS fans for 2007, but we need as many home pages of authors as we can!

To all readers and contributors: submissions for 2007 are steadily coming in, so stay tuned, submit a good paper yourself and encourage others to do so, and make sure that our computer science world will use J.UCS still more than it did in the past. To the members of the editorial board and all other reviewers: thanks for your help, your support and many valuable suggestions.

Since this is the last issue of 2006, let me (a bit late) wish you also the very best for 2007,

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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